

The Velocity Potential for Schlogl's Model

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Manuscript received 7 February 1997, revised 27 June 1997, accepted 30 September 1997

It is shown that velocity potential for a simple nonlinear reaction scheme involving a simple chemical intermediate (Schlogl's model) exists. The system shows two steady states and transformation from one steady state to the another is admissible. The first state has been shown to be less stable than the second state.

There is considerable current interest on multiple steady states, since bistability has been experimentally observed in a number of chemical systems¹, although theoretical models had been proposed from time to time. Amongst these, Schlogl's model² is the simplest and we shall use this for examining whether transformation from one steady state to the other is permissible or not. This question has arisen in the context of recent observations of the chemical wave³, displaying bistability. Experimental results indicate that such waves are associated with the transformation of one steady state to another.

Prigogine⁴ showed that in the domain of the validity of the thermodynamics of irreversible processes, the contribution of the time change of the forces to the entropy production is negative or zero, so that

$$d_x\sigma = \sum J_k dx_k \leq 0 \quad (1)$$

where σ is the entropy production, and J_k and x_k denote the conjugate fluxes and forces respectively. For the case of chemical reactions,

$$d_x\sigma = \sum J_k d(A_k/T) \leq 0 \quad (2)$$

where A_k is the affinity of the reaction rate (2). It should be noted that $d_x\sigma$ is frequently not an exact differential, hence it is not of much use. However, for certain situations,

$$Td_x\sigma = dD \quad (3)$$

so that D can be considered to be a velocity potential⁴.

The purpose of the present work is to examine whether such a velocity potential exists for Schlogl's model which involves the following steps,

so that the net reaction is $A \rightarrow B$. The first step (4) is autocatalytic. Kinetic equations for the rate of change of X are non-linear, and the steady state solutions coupled with linear stability analysis show that the system is stable. The reaction rates J_1 and J_2 for the two reaction steps (4 and 5) are given by

$$J_1 = k_1AX^2 - k_2X^3 \quad (6)$$

$$J_2 = k_3X - k_4B \quad (7)$$

where k_1 and k_2 are the forward and backward rate constants for reaction (4); similarly, k_3 and k_4 are for the reaction (5). The symbols A , B and X in equations (6) and (7) denote the concentration of the respective species. The affinities A_1 and A_2 of reactions (4) and (5) respectively, can be written as

$$A_1 = RT \ln K_1 - RT \ln X/B \quad (8)$$

$$A_2 = RT \ln K_2 - RT \ln B/X \quad (9)$$

where K_1 and K_2 are the equilibrium constants of the reactions (4) and (5). Differentiating eqns. (8) and (9) with respect to X , we get

$$\frac{dA_1}{dt} = -\frac{RT}{X} \frac{dX}{dt}$$

$$\frac{dA_2}{dt} = \frac{RT}{X} \frac{dX}{dt}$$

Hence, we can write,

$$dD = J_1 dA_1 + J_2 dA_2 = \frac{RT}{X} (k_2X^3 - k_1AX^2 + k_3X - k_4B) dX \quad (10)$$

On integration, we get,

$$D = RT \left(\frac{k_2X^3}{3} - \frac{k_1AX^2}{2} + k_3X - k_4B \ln X + C \right) \quad (11)$$

where C is the constant of integration. In principle, one can plot D as a function of X , provided C is known.

Putting $k_2 = 3$, $k_1A = 2$, $k_3 = 9.8 \times 10^{-4}$, $k_4B = 2.53 \times 10^{-8}$, $R = 1.98 \text{ cal K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and $T = 298 \text{ K}$, eqn. (11) may be written as

$$D = 590 X^3 - 590 X^2 + 0.6 X - 1.5 \times 10^{-5} \ln X + C \quad (12)$$

C may be calculated by putting $X = D = 1$,

$$D = 590 X^3 - 590 X^2 + 0.6 X - 1.5 \times 10^{-5} \ln X + 71.48 \times 10^{-5} \quad (13)$$

D vs X plot of eqn. (13) is shown in Fig. 1. Due to the long range of X and D values, three separate plots (a), (b) and (c) are shown for three different regions. Here, we are more interested in potential minima or maxima. It is evident from Fig. 1 that eqn. (13) consists of two minima and one maximum. There are two states I and II when the velocity

Fig. 1. Plot of D against X .

potential is minimum. The state with lower D (Fig. 1c) will be more stable and steepness k of the minimum is given by

$$k = \frac{(d^2D/dX^2)}{[1 + (dD/dX)^2]^{3/2}} \quad (14)$$

The corresponding values of k for the first and the second minima are found to be 8.8×10^{-4} and 7.3×10^{-3} respectively, showing that although the first state is less stable than the second one, the tendency for crossing the maximum might be more in the case of the second minimum.

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